

R.W. Emerson's Transcendentalism and Advaita Vedanta: A Comparative Study

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Abstract:

The objective of this paper is to analyse R.W Emersons Transcendentalism and non-dualistic Indian thought. This paper attempts to study the purpose of human life according to R.W Emerson and its affinity with Vedantic concept of Jeevan Mukti. The 19th century American Society witnessed new trends in art, culture, religion and philosophy. New England young intellectuals embraced new thoughts and ideas and attempted to redefine American Religious Culture, Philosophy and Literature. This religious philosophical and literary movement was known as Transcendentalism in the history of American literature. The Transcendentalists revolted against established traditions and tried to construct new philosophy. The young intellectuals advocated divinity of man, purity of human heart and individualism. The young intellectuals propagated their ideas through their literary works under the leadership of R.W Emerson. This paper upholds all parallelisms in American Transcendentalism and Advaita Vedanta.

Keywords: Swedenborgian, Transcendentalism, Advaita Vedanta, Idealism, phenomenal world, illusion, Mayavaada, YogaNidra, Soteriological.

Introduction:

The unitarian theology which emphasized on the significance of external evidence in the spiritual enlightenment could not win the hearts of 19th century American young intellectuals. Calvinism which advocated the doctrine of "original sin" could not satisfy the spiritual quest of new England intellectuals. A group of learned scholars under the leadership of R.W Emerson rebelled against orthodox Christianity and preached new religious philosophy. The transcendentalists introduced Spiritualism and redefined the orthodox

theology with their new ideas.

R.W Emerson in his first work the Nature advocated oneness of man, nature and God. In his divinity school address condemned historical Christianity and articulated the impersonality of God. In his essay "Over Soul" published in 1841 Emerson propounded the divinity of man. According to him

the God (Over soul) contains all beings in him and all creatures leave in him. All individual souls are part and parcel of the over soul and all the souls are connected to one another. Thus, Emerson with his doctrine of Over soul advocated new spiritualism.

Emerson articulated the concept of "God within" and strongly advised whole humanity to realize the god within or true self and to experience oneness with the absolute. According to him history, traditions, religion and scriptures play no role in the individual spiritual evolution. Emerson strongly believed that every man has essential resources which to attain spiritual enlightenment. The transcendentalists strongly advocated self-reliance as the means of self-realization.

Transcendentalism says that man due to his ignorance misidentifies himself with ego and neglects in his true self. The individual can realize God within only through spiritual regeneration and obeying the intuition. Emerson explained the limitations of human intellect and suggested his contemporaries to depend upon intuition. The Transcendentalists rejected the authority of religious institutions and scriptures on individual the young intellectuals propounded new theology based on the ideas which they imbibed from various religions and cultures. Oriental Mysticism, German Idealism, British Romanticism and Ancient Greek Philosophy shaped the philosophy of Transcendentalists.

R.W Emerson was born in the family of religious priests and was introduced to harsh realities of the world in his childhood after the death of his father. He pursued his graduation in Harvard university and completed religious studies in Harvard divinity school. The Harvard university introduced Indian thought to young Emerson. Emerson's aunt Mary Moody encouraged Emerson to delve into Vedantic literature. He acknowledges the depth of Hindu religious thought and developed passion for Vedic literature. He confessed the greatness of Indian philosophy. "India teaches through its clouds of legends, has yet a simple and grand religion, like a queenly countenance seen through a rich veil. It teaches to speak the truth, love others as you, and to despise trifles. The East is grand, and makes & Europe a land of trifles". (Journals. Vol. VII. Pp.120-30). Emerson realized the affinity between his thoughts and Vedanta philosophy and used few ideas to strengthen his philosophy. Frequent reference to Vedantic concepts and quoting lines from Vedic literature doesn't mean that Vedanta philosophy shaped Emerson's thought.

R.W Emerson in his first work nature articulated the basic tenants of his philosophy. He

propounded his spiritualism in the last three chapters in his work. For him the nature is the best spiritual teacher and universal mind reflects in the nature. "Have mountains, and waves, and skies, not significance but what we consciously give them when we employ them as emblems of our thoughts? The world is emblematic" (Works. Vol. I. P. 32) according to Emerson the god speaks through nature he suggests mankind to read the divine mind through literature. God reveals his mind through the elements of the nature. He says "as gravity, centripetence, repulsion, polarity, undulation, has a counterpart in the intellect" (Works. Vol. III. P. 211). Emerson's work nature defines the world as mere reflection of the absolute being.

Emerson refers every empirical object as an apocalypse of the mind. He believes that individual can understand the divine design by decoding the nature for him the oversoul (God) is the cause and the world is mere appearance it is neither real nor unreal. In this work he writes "It is the uniform

effect of culture on the human mind, not to shake our faith in the stability of particular phenomena as of heat, Water, azote; but to lead us to regard nature as phenomenon, not substance; to attribute necessary existence to spirit; to esteem nature as an accident and an effect" (works. Vol. P. 49).

For idealists the matter is nothing and they give importance to ideas. Therefore, idealism advocates that the phenomenal world is the by-product of human mind and sensations. He says "Mind is the only reality, of which men and all other natures are better or worse reflectors" (Works. Vol. P. 33. "The Transcendentalist"). Like an idealist Emerson considers the oversoul as absolute truth and source of the creation. He accepted the idealism of Vyasa and admired the Vedantic philosophy which defined the transient and immutable as eternal and temporal and visible as unreal. Vedanta treats all empirical objects as unreal. Emerson also emphasizes the same in his works "Things we now esteem fixed shall, one by one, detach themselves like ripe fruit from our experience, and fall, The landscape, the figures, Boston, London are facts as fugitive as any institution past, or any institution past, or any whiff of mist or smoke, and so is society and so is the world. The soul looketh steadily, forwards, creating a world before her, leaving worlds behind her. She has no dates, nor rites, nor persons, nor specialties, nor men. The soul knows the only the soul; the web of events is tiling flowing robe in which she is clothed."

Emerson in his work nature expounds the universal soul as all pervasive impersonal and attributeless absolute truth. This very idea echoes Vedantic concept of Nirguna Brahma. For Emerson and Vedanta, the world is mere appearance and universal being manifests itself with various names and forms in the world. Therefore, both Emerson and Vedanta suggest to overcome the delusive power of the world to realize the absolute truth. Thus, Emerson's doctrine of illusion and Vedantic concept of Maya advocated similar ideas. According to the both there is only one reality and that exists in all beings. For Emerson and Vedanta nothing exists except the absolute every being emanates from the absolute and exists in it. Therefore,

the subjective and objective distinction doesn't prevail. Vedanta says Ekam Advitiam Brahma similarly Emerson also articulated oneness of Man, Nature and God in "*Nature*".

Emerson strongly criticized the assumptions of materialists and propagated spiritualism like an idealist for him the spirit is the cause and the world is the effect. He considers the matter as dead mind. These idealistic tendencies in him made the scholars to believe the influence of Plato's Idealism on Emerson's Philosophy. Emerson in his works clearly mentioned the influence of eastern thought on Plato, he called Plato as half Orientalist. According to Emerson Plato succeeded in maintaining perfect balance between the orient and the oxidant. Emerson writes "The unity of Asia and the detail of Europe; Plato came to join... The excellences of Europe Asia are in his brain"(works, Vol. IV. P.40.Plato). Emerson's reading of Plato inspired him to study Vedanta philosophy after 1845 Emerson extensively read Vedantic literature including *Upanishads*, *Bhagavad Geeta* and *Bhagavad Purana*. *Isha Upanishad* introduced the concept of Brahma to Emerson which lend support in formulating his doctrine of oversoul. *Bruhadaranyaka Upanishad* introduced the nature of the world, *Bhagavad Geeta* provided concepts like compensation (Karma), balancing mind (Stitapragna) and *Bhagavata purana* and *Vishnu purana* supplied the concept of maya to Emerson. Vedanta philosophy strengthened Emerson's idealism which he propounded in his first work *Nature*. Emerson clearly defined transcendentalism as Idealism when he says "What is popularly called Transcendentalism among us is idealism; Idealism as it appeared" (Works. Vol. 329-30, "The Transcendentalist"). Like Vedanta Emerson echoes many idealistic views in his work *Nature* he says "Idealism saith: matter is a phenomenon, not a substance. Idealism acquaints us with the total disparity between the evidence of our own being and the evidence of the world's being, the one is perfect, the other, incapable of my assurance, the mind is a part of the nature of things; world is a divine dream, from which we may presently awake to the glories and certainties of day" (Works. Vol, I, P. 62, "Nature").

Unlike materialists the idealists define the world as phenomenal. idealism defines the absolute being as ultimate reality which is beyond all constraints and attributes. Vedanta and Emerson argue that individual cannot comprehend the infinitude with finite mind. *Taitreya Upanishad* says that mind cannot comprehend the power by which it is able to think. *Kena Upanishad* similarly describes as there the eye goes not, speech goes not, nor the mind; we know not, we understand not how one would teach it. Both Emerson and Vedanta articulate that the absolute being infinite and attribute less can be realized through experience, they further argue that no one can explain or disseminate knowledge of the absolute because the language can't describe the nature of the absolute. Thus, both condemn the role of religious scriptures, institutions and rituals in realization of God. In self-reliance he says "And now at last the highest truth on this subject (self-reliance) remains unsaid; probably cannot be said; for all that we say is the far-off remembering of the intuition" (Works. Vol.11. -Pp. 68-69, "Self-Reliance). Emerson and Vedanta advocate that one can realize the absolute only through intuition. For them God dwells in every being and realizing God within is the purpose of

human life. The one who depends upon external sources can't realize the God within. For them the individual soul is identical with the universal soul. Upanishads propound the doctrine of Ahambrahmaasmi (I am the absolute), the doctrine of Tatvamasī (Thou art that), Aiyam Brahma (The self is Brahma) and Pragnanam Brahma (Brahma is consciousness), all these doctrines establish the fact that man is none other than the Absolute but he is not able to recognize his true self due to his ignorance. The ultimate purpose of life is to realize the true self and to rely upon the self, Emerson rightly called it Self-reliance.

Emerson and Vedanta affirm that every being emanates from the absolute. Emerson writes in his essay "...within man is the soul of the whole; the wise silence; the Universal beauty, to which every part and parcel is equally related; the eternal ONE" (Works. Vol. 11. P. 269, "The Over-soul"). Emerson through all his works advocates the doctrine of infinitude of a private man. Man being finite can't comprehend God within due to his ignorance. Emerson and Vedanta strongly advocate oneness of man and God and argue that the individual can attain self-realization by depending upon God within therefore Emerson's self-reliance means God reliance. Both Emerson and Vedanta consider the nature as the best means to realize the absolute. Emerson writes "The Idealist says, God paints the world around your soul, the spiritualist saith, yea, but God is within you, the self of self Creates the world through you..." (Journals. Vol. IV. 78.) Both Vedanta and Emerson attributed soteriological value to the phenomenal world. According to both men can realize the God by unveiling the illusive screen of name and form, like Vedanta Emerson through his Idealism preached spiritualism and divinity of man.

Conclusion:

R.W Emerson initially relied upon Berkeleyan Idealism and Swedenborg's philosophy. After reading Vedantic literature in 1845 Emerson depended upon Advaita Vedanta to enrich his philosophy. Emerson like Vedantic preached spiritualism and divinity of man through his works till his last breath.

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